

*Equality Diversity and Inclusion for
Research Enhancement in Bosnia Herzegovina*

EDiRE

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Deliverable abstract

The project Equality Diversity and Inclusion for Research Enhancement in Bosnia Herzegovina (EDIRE) will produce and disseminate an innovative model for increasing the research profile of SSST, boosting its research capacity, especially in the field of Equality, Diversity, and Inclusion (EDI).

This is the updated version of the Dissemination, Communication, Exploitation Plan of the EDIRE project planned for M18.

EDIRE builds upon the knowledge and experience held within the consortium to introduce and implement new lines of research at SSST in relation to EDI to enhance excellence in research. These transversal EDI research areas will be embedded in an intensive set of training and networking actions aimed at boosting SSST research and management capacity.

For the achievement of such objectives, the project relies on a eclectic set of methods, such as:

- 1) interdisciplinarity and knowledge sharing,
- 2) capacity building,
- 3) participatory approach,
- 4) inclusivity and sustainability,
- 5) far-reaching methods for communication and engagement,
- 6) Responsible Research and Innovation.

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1. Introduction

The first version of Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation Plan (DCEP) (**D6.1, M3**) described strategies, target groups, schedules of dissemination and communication activities and specific measures, while also including the respective key performance indicators and assessment means. Following on this, D6.2 Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation Package – RP1 (M18) contains all dissemination products prepared during the first 18 months of the project.

The present DCE Package includes: all promotional materials developed; snapshots describing main sections of the project website; references regarding social media use; EC dissemination tools employed including radio and TV broadcasting; text of all the press releases published; the press conferences organized and related press reviews; agenda of the attended events external to the project and the presentations given; agenda, presentations and participants' satisfaction questionnaire regarding the project events organized in P1; references to all publications produced in the reporting period, as well as information on liaison activities.

1.1 COVID-19-related measures

As a result of COVID-19, EDIRE will adapt its activities if necessary. The Consortium will adjust its activities in accordance with the instructions of all partners' institutions regarding COVID-19. Meetings and visits will be conducted online if the measures prevent in-person meetings or travel.

1.2 Abbreviations/Acronyms

DCEP- The Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation Plan

EDI- Equality, Diversity, Inclusion

2. Strategy planning

During the early stages of EDIRE, efforts focused on establishing its visual identity through consortium partner proposals and planning materials for the website and social media. An inaugural event was also held to launch the project's dissemination and communication activities, which simultaneously supported the establishment of the project's exploitation in line with planned strategies.

2.1 Dissemination Strategy

2.1.1 Internal Strategy

SSST's internal strategy involved enhancing networking activities with partners and improving research management capabilities by involving various departments (Computer Science, Medical School, Economics, Political Science), staff (academic and administrative), and students (postgraduates and advanced undergraduates). Partners played a key role in promoting EDI, GM, and GE, utilizing their contacts with decision-makers and experts to form internal working groups to carry out core project activities. These groups included departments or institutions that are already either developing or implementing EDI policies.

2.1.2 External Strategy

EDIRE's results and findings were disseminated both nationally and internationally. The consortium utilized communication activities to promote EDIRE actions and results, targeting the public, engaged stakeholders, and the media, primarily through social media, the website, and press releases. Project outputs, outcomes, and other core aspects of the project process were shared with expert and organizational audiences through conferences, journal articles, and other scientific dissemination methods. Additionally, project exploitation activities aimed to encourage the adoption of strategies and plans developed within the project, as well as to distribute policy recommendations among key stakeholders, targeting these audiences in both the short and medium term.

https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/docs/h2020-funding-guide/imgs/quick-guide_diss-expl_en.pdf

2.2 Communication Strategy

EDIRE's communication strategy was devised to cultivate widespread awareness of the project in the public domain and to inform all stakeholders, particularly those beyond the scientific community, about the project's added value. The accomplishments, discoveries, and methodologies developed by EDIRE were to be disseminated at local, regional, national, and international levels. Efficient knowledge transfer to engage with the project's primary target groups were to be facilitated through various selected channels and activities. These included the establishment of EDIRE's website and regular updates, along with the distribution of newsletters and the publication of scientific articles in Open Access international peer-reviewed journals. Additionally, promotional materials that could be easily disseminated were to be produced. Various events and liaison activities were planned to serve as channels for distributing EDIRE's findings to diverse audiences, including researchers, students at various educational levels, research institutes, businesses (both small and large), universities, policymakers, and the public.

The higher education system in Bosnia and Herzegovina is rather complex, with no centralized Ministry for Higher Education or Science at the national level. Instead, small departments within the Ministry of Civil Affairs cover these topics. Additionally, in the two entities (Republic Srpska, RS and Federation BH, FBH), these matters are addressed either at the entity level (RS) or cantonal level (FBH). Given this, notable efforts have been made in the project to establish a relationship with the Ministry of Science, Higher Education and Youth in the Canton Sarajevo, and the Minister herself participated as a speaker during EDIRE's Kick-off Meeting. With recent elections in Bosnia and Herzegovina and pending changes in the cantonal government, plans were in place to strengthen this relationship and keep relevant authorities updated on EDIRE's developments.

Furthermore, stronger relationships were being forged with ten other research institutions throughout the country. and these efforts were directed towards leveraging these connections to engage with policymakers across Bosnia and Herzegovina. Given the project's European scope, stakeholders included the Delegation of the European Union in Bosnia and Herzegovina, universities with significant achievements in the EDI domain, and embassies of EU countries, particularly those represented by EDIRE's partners.

International media were targeted through a communication strategy designed to raise public awareness of the project outcomes and potential exploitation. Partners' press offices, equipped with experience in preparing press releases, announcements, and media materials, were to support this communication strategy.

2.3 Dissemination and Communication channels and indicators

As part of the dissemination and communication process, the following channels will be setup and maintained (their impact will be accessed using the predetermined indicators as target values, e.g. key performance indicators (KPIs))

Type	Details
<p><i>Project website (M1-M36)</i></p>	<p>The website is aimed not only at experts in the field but also at society (such as students, families, teachers, and citizens) with the final goal to amplify the project's intended impact. The initial version of the website will be online by M3 and it will include project partners, aims, expected impacts. The website will be further developed to include public deliverables, events calendar, and links to social network tools, together with a section containing possible answers to resistance questions. The Private area will be intended for project partners and Project Officer.</p> <p>The core pages of the website will describe success stories regarding the twinning activities. Main project success stories will be published in English and translated into BCS. Such sections of the project website will be clear and comprehensive to reach audiences with different educational levels and cultural backgrounds. The separate section of the website will be specialized for different fields of research so that the audience can find more targeted information. To gain broader audience, the social media posts will always reference the website.</p> <p>Assessment strategy: 1) Indicator: number of hits; 2) Target Values: >2000 by the end of Y1, >3600 by the end of project life; 3) Means of verification: Reports from website facility for counting number of accesses.</p>
<p><i>Promotional material (M3)</i></p>	<p>A catchy project logo will be designed and used in all communication material to establish the project's visual identity at the very beginning. Flyers, brochures, and advertisements boards will be ready by M3 and adopted in all consortium languages to ensure dissemination activities within events of various nature and on relevant public spaces. To ensure sustainability, we will print only a limited number of promotional materials, aiming to make the most of the distribution electronically. Assessment strategy: 1) Indicator: N. of brochures created and distributed; 2) Target Values: >1500 by the end of Y1, >3000 by the end of project life; 3) Means of verification: Distribution via events and through partners' channels.</p>

Dissemination

Additional dissemination channels that EDIRE will use are:

Type	Details
Open access scientific publications (M6-M36)	A minimum of five scientific articles will be published in open access international peer-reviewed journals adhering to HE Open Access policy, targeting especially peer-reviewed flagship publications in the field. In BA, the following top indexed journals will be targeted for publications: Periodicals of Engineering and Natural Sciences, Bosnian Journal of Basic Medical Sciences, Medicinski Arhiv, Acta Informatica Medica, Southeast European Journal of Economics and Business. Other peer-reviewed international journals related to EDI and similar topics: Equality, Diversity and Inclusion: An International Journal; International Journal of Information, Diversity, & Inclusion; AG-About Gender; Gender & Society; Disability and Society; International Journal of Disability Development and Education, American Journal of Sociology and Anthropology; Journal of Higher Education Policy and Management, International Journal of Gender, Science and Technology and others to be identified by the researchers and all partners in their research domain, chosen at the beginning of the activities, also at national level. <i>Assessment strategy</i> Indicator: N° of articles; 1) Target Values: At least 5 accepted submissions at the end of the project; 2) Means of verification: List of publications inserted in SyGMa.

Project Newsletter (M6-36)	A project newsletter will be produced by SSST on a six-month basis. It will be available on the project website and distributed to other relevant research institutions and universities in BA. The Newsletter will be translated in BCS. It will inform about the past, ongoing and future project activities and include short interviews to stakeholders and partners' members. <i>Assessment strategy:</i> 1) Indicator: N° of issues and N° of addressees. 2) Target Values: ≥6 issues (2/year); at least 500 addressees for each issue in Y1, with a 10% increase per year; 3) Means of verification: E-Newsletter on the website and number of downloads and e-mails sent.
Liaison activities (M6-M36)	The consortium will liaise with international, EU, national, international projects on the same, or similar, issues, thus exchanging good practices and ideas, contributing to mainstreaming and then constantly updating the developed results. Particular attention will be devoted to initiatives funded in the WB, also out of the present call. <i>Assessment strategy:</i> 1) Indicator: N° of EU funded project addressed; 2) Target Values: at least 3 projects during the project overall duration; 3) Means of verification: Contents of dissemination and communication packages (D6.3 and D6.4)

Communication

The additional communication tools that EDIRE will utilize are:

Type	Details
Social media (M1-M36)	<p>EDIRE Social Media Strategy will communicate information on ongoing activities, publications etc., to stakeholders and the public mainly through LinkedIn, Twitter, Facebook, YouTube (other media will be considered in time, if necessary). EDIRE will use established social media accounts of EDIRE's partners to interact with target audiences and the public in all consortium countries. Established Facebook accounts will be helpful to interact with existing networks. Specific project hashtags will be selected and used for quantitative assessment. A Blog will be established, and posts will be disseminated also through social media channels (cf. T6.6, point 2). <u>Assessment strategy</u></p> <p>Indicator: N° of Likes and Shares, Tweets and Retweets with certain selected hashtags; N° of participants to initiatives; N° of publications on the web blog; 2) Target Values: at least 10% increase per year, after Y1 (starting from a baseline on 500 contacts per partner) as for the N° of followers; at least 5 publications on the web blog (videos, photos, articles) by M36; 3) Means of verification: reports from such networks to be kept alive via regular posting and monitoring; blog statistics.</p>
Press releases and media relations (M1-M36)	<p>Project results and milestones will also be communicated and disseminated through media (general press, magazines for audiences interested in EDI initiatives) via press releases and press briefings. EDIRE will strive at maximum geographical coverage beyond the countries represented in the consortium, with a special focus on BA and other widening countries characterized by similar situations. Presentations of project results will also be issued, whenever possible, to radio and television. Besides, EDIRE will also use the freely accessible EC tools (e.g. CORDIS Wire, CORDIS News, Horizon Magazine, research*eu, "Futuris" and "Innovation" Magazines on Euronews, Athena Web) to ensure successful project communication. Assessment strategy: 1) Indicator: N° of quotes on newspapers, television, websites; Radio and TV contributions; 2) Target Values: At least 15 articles in either newspaper/magazines/radio by the end of the project; at least 2 reports per year on radio/TV programmes by M36; 3) Means of verification: Proof of publications or videos.</p>
Participation in Open-Science events (M6-M36)	<p>Participation in the following events will be secured: a) Participation in the Science Festivals will be ensured by all project partners; b) "Public" sessions with invited speakers: participation in open sessions, panels and debates (number of events and of visitors will be collected); c) School fairs will also be targeted in all EDIRE countries, to engage future HE students in understanding EDI's relevance. Assessment strategy. d) organisation of events with students' organisations and existing student HUBs e) participation in already established annual events (Researcher's Night, 16 days of Activism against Gender-based Violence and similar) 1) Indicator: N° of events where EDIRE is presented and promoted; 2) Target Values: >3 events attended during the project; 3) Means of verification: Attendance proof, presented material, photos, events' reports.</p>

2.4 Exploitation Strategy

Below EDIRE overall strategy for exploiting projects' results:

- 1) The approaches developed in EDIRE together with its results will be replicated in other academic institutions in BA and beyond, as well as in the society and at policy level. EDIRE results will represent an intermediate step towards the consolidation of a new and collaborative research line on EDI in BA, which will trigger the establishment of cultural inclusion programmes, with a trans- and interdisciplinary approach. This will also trigger the implementation of a new set of research and innovation projects within the participant organisations and outside. Therefore, one of the components of the strategy for exploitation of results, in the short term, is the promotion and development of these new projects.
- 2) Recommendations and good practices to improve research management and fundraising capacities. EDIRE results, especially the good practices identified for the enhancement of research management and fundraising, will be fully exploited as detailed in what follows: a) all the activities planned to reinforce the participation of a widening country in EU funded research will be exploited and transferred towards other countries to plan goals, performance and training needs for future projects involvement; b) the establishment of a set of templates and tools which will be made available in the intranet of SSST (see T5.3). They will be used by all researchers and administrative staff for writing and managing other projects, also after EDIRE end-date.
- 3) Training materials: all the materials resulting from the EDIRE training courses have been made available in a public format.
- 4) As SSST started as an IT University, it has strong partners in the IT sector and is looking to further strengthen the economic impact in this sector. Through the EDIRE mobilities, additional European partners will join the list of existing contacts of the hosting institutions. In addition, the researchers will also learn about the technology transfer processes that exist at the European Universities. Formal agreements to institutionalize the contacts developed during the project will be established, paying special attention to the new business partners met during the staff exchange activities, thus creating the conditions for ensuring that EDIRE results will impact on the BA economic system.

As regards IPR, it is to be noted that EDIRE is a CSA not involving technology development activities. In any case, a pre-agreement on the overall IPR strategy has already been agreed upon in the following terms (which is further detailed in the CA - Consortium Agreement): "foreground IP shall be owned by the partner carrying out the work leading to it; if new IP is created jointly by at least 2 partners, and it is impossible to distinguish between their contributions, such IP will be jointly owned by all contributing parties. For policy development

and the further promotion of innovation, the European Commission will be given a non-exclusive royalty-free licence to use the EDiRE public knowledge, which will be further detailed in the CA". As stated in the CA, the Steering Committee will make the IP related decisions and a partner which can show that its intellectual property rights or other legitimate interests would be severely affected by a Steering Committee decision, may exercise a veto with respect to the corresponding decision or relevant part of the decision.

Specific qualitative measurements were elaborated during the first 10 months of the project. These derived from the needs' recognition and the subsequent drafting of the Strategic plan for enhancing scientific excellence in D3.2. Qualitative KPIs.

3 Activities Overview due M18

As part of the dissemination and communication process, the following channels have been setup and maintained (EDIRE team created KPIs table updating it time-to-time based on the project activities and workflow):

Type	Details								
Project website (M1-M36)	<p>EDIRE established official Project Website with the following sections:</p> <p>EDIRE – the main page with the short descriptions of the objectives of the EDIRE project</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Partners – the list of all EDIRE partners with the contacts ▪ Advisory board – the list of all Advisory Board Members and institutions they are representing ▪ News – posts with all project activities and dissemination events where partners participating. All news has been categorized by different category sections such as: Project Activity, Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation Activity and Project Meeting. ▪ Publications – section for public deliverables and EDIRE Newsletter issues ▪ Blog – section for EDIRE partners and all others who wants to contribute by dissemination activity through opinion overviews. ▪ Trainings – Website section for all EDIRE trainings provided by EDIRE partners (contained by training announcements) ▪ Project Docs – special section for limited access (project documents relevant to reporting periods) <p style="text-align: center;"><i>Image 1: EDIRE Website Sections Screenshot</i></p>	Indicator: Number of hits	Website link	Means of verification: Reports from the website facility for counting number of accesses.	YEAR	3028	www.edire.eu	LINK (TABLE 1)	1
Indicator: Number of hits	Website link	Means of verification: Reports from the website facility for counting number of accesses.	YEAR						
3028	www.edire.eu	LINK (TABLE 1)	1						

Promotional material (M3)

EDiRE team agreed and designed project promotional material available on project Website under following subpages:

- [Project flyer](#)
- [Project Brochure](#)

Project flyers and brochures have been disseminated according to DCEP participating in all events, project activities. Also, stakeholders have been well-informed, and flyers and brochure were sent to their email addresses.

Image 3: Project flyer example

Image 4: Project Brochure example

Table 2: KPI Brochure Table

Project brochures	Indicator: Nº of brochures created and distributed (printed version)	Indicator: Nº of brochures created and distributed (printed version and addresses)	Means of verification: Distribution via events and through partners' channels.	YEAR
The first edition	200	1682	Link	1

In line with the DCEP Stakeholder identification and the theory of the organizational and business management sector (R.R. Freeman, 1984) EDIRE partners followed four steps that involved the creation of a register of stakeholders who have been targeted in dissemination activities such as sending Newsletter issues; an analysis of stakeholders to understand each stakeholder's needs and interests; classify them into meaningful groups based on the potential power and interest they could have in the project; involve them in communication activities, especially using Social Media platforms.

Three Newsletters have been issued and publicized on Website subpage:

[Newsletter I](#)

[Newsletter II](#)

[Newsletter III](#)

Image 5: The first page of EDIRE Newsletters

Image 6: The content of EDIRE Newsletter – example

EDIRE supporting students in Bosnia and Herzegovina in EDI activities

The EDIRE team member, Cinzia Leone from the University of Genova, Italy gave an online lecture on Equality, Diversity and Inclusion, and Gender Equality Plan for students from Sarajevo, Bosnia, and Herzegovina. The talk was organized by the Association for the development of education, science, and research from BiH, and it was held online.

The professor from UniGe had the opportunity to present EDIRE and underline the importance of research in academia. By explaining what EDI principles are, Leone explained how the EDIRE project would enhance research in BiH. Apart from that, students heard more about gender in general and gender equality in Europe.

[Read more](#)

The Second project meeting and panel discussion: Research, university, gender, and EDI principles

February 16th, 2023

As the project implementation began, the first six months were marked by a number of meetings, plans, surveys, and planning activities. The second project meeting was organized online on February 16th, which included internal meetings among partners as well as a public event with distinguished speakers.

We had the great honor of engaging in discussions with professors from Bulgaria, Bosnia and Herzegovina, and Italy regarding universities, gender, EDI principles, and research. Our esteemed speakers included Prof. Lyuba Spasova from the Bulgarian Academy of Science, Prof. Sarina Bakic from the University of Sarajevo, Prof. Paolo Piccardo from the University of Genova, and Prof. Davide Peddis, also from the University of Genova.

The panel discussion was skillfully moderated by Prof. Jasminka Hasic Telalovic from the University SSST.

[Read more](#)

[Youtube link](#)

National consultations: Universities and Research centers

March 27th, 2023

The national consultations were organized with universities and research centers to discuss important issues related to research, projects, funding, and EDI principles, and to explore ways to strengthen collaboration and partnerships among institutions.

The participants explored various ways to strengthen collaboration and partnerships among institutions, including joint research projects, student and faculty exchange programs, and the sharing of resources and expertise.

Overall, the consultations a great success, providing a valuable platform for the exchange of ideas and insights among like-minded individuals who share a passion for promoting equality, diversity, and inclusion in research.

[Read more](#)

Overcoming Obstacles and Seizing Opportunities in Europe's Research and Innovation Landscape

June 1st, 2023

In a recent event, Associate Professor Jasminka Hasic Telalovic shared her expertise and insights on the Horizon program and projects. She highlighted two notable projects: EDIRE, coordinated by SSST, and Budget-IT, in which the University is a proud partner.

<i>Table 3: KPI Newsletter</i>			
Project Newsletter	Indicator: N° of issues and N° of addressees	Means of verification: E-Newsletter on the website and number of downloads and e-mails sent	Year
The first Newsletter	Issue 1: 967	LINK 1	Y1
The second Newsletter	Issue 2: 876	LINK 2	
The third Newsletter	Issue 3: 967	LINK 3	

Dissemination

Additional dissemination channels that EDIRE have been using:

Type	Details
Open access scientific publications (M6-M36)	<p>EDIRE team have been working on the following publications:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ G. Arena, A. C. Taramasso, Gender mainstreaming policies in Italian universities: actors, tools, documents, IPPA Conference Paper, 2023 (to be published) ▪ R. Bencivenga, C. Leone, C. M. Reale, J. Hasic Telalovic, Transforming academia through equality, diversity, and inclusion: the experience of Bosnia and Herzegovina with the EDIRE project, in A. Tuselli, C. M. Reale, A. Donà, M. M. Coppola (eds.), Gender R-evolutions, Conference proceedings, 2024 (to be published) ▪ Dž. Bašić, J. Hasić Telalović, L. Pašić (SSST), Autism Spectrum Disorder in Children from Bosnia and Herzegovina, Microbime and Machine Learning, Volume II (to be published) ▪ Journal of Gender Studies, Special Issue “Gender and academic employment in changing times” edited by R. Rosa, S. Clavero and G. Strachan (forthcoming 2024). ▪ R. Bencivenga, C. M. Reale, Harmonised GEPs report, EDIRE Public Deliverable, D3.3, 10.5281/zenodo.10632670 (DOI), Zenodo, 10.5281/zenodo.10632708, Zenodo ▪ S. Clavero, C. Delaney, Preliminary guidelines and recommendation on EDI, Public Deliverable, D2.2, ▪ C.M Reale, A. Celeste Taramasso, Interim report and evaluation on the expertise development activities, Public Deliverable, D5.2, 10.5281/zenodo.10728035, Zenodo <p>EDIRE created Zenodo profile to publish all relevant project documents and upcoming publications.</p>

	and Beyond, Dublin, October 2023 <i>See Annex 1</i>			4. Jeanne McDonagh (Open Doors Initiative, Ireland)		
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Table 5: Group 2: Gathering representatives of all the key EDIRE target groups (to be organised in June 2024 and September 2025)

GROUP 2 (G2): gathering representatives of all the key EDIRE target groups, will be organised	Project dissemination events
Target Values: >50 external participants per event, Target Values: >10 participants per event	Mid-term dissemination event to be organized in June 2024 Spain by UCM to present main project findings, where an active role will be given to SSST staff to create fruitful networking opportunities (it will be co-located with the first summer school)
	Final dissemination event to be organized in M35 in BA by SSST to present final project findings (it will be co-located with the second summer school) and with the Mediterranean Forum. The final event will thus involve a wide variety of stakeholders' representatives (i.e. academic and research sector, policy makers, civil society organizations, non-governmental organizations, etc.) and it will be an excellent occasion to present and validate all key project outcomes.

Table 6: Group 3: Gathering representatives of all the key EDIRE target groups (to be organised in June 2024 and September 2025)

GROUP 3 (G3). Events external to the consortium activities. Participation of consortium members will be secured in external events of relevance with respect to the issues tackled by EDIRE and targeting both scientific and nonscientific community	Events external to the consortium activities	Indicator: N° of events attended where EDIRE is presented and promoted	Means of verification: Attendance proof, presented material, photos, events' reports	Project Year
Target Values: >10 attended external events during the project	EDIRE supporting students in Bosnia and Herzegovina in EDI activities (November 2022)	1	https://edire.eu/?p=196	1
	Public engagement in R&I – Science education and Gender Equality in Science (December 2022)	1	https://edire.eu/?p=193	1
	Gender R-Evolutions conference (November 2022)	1	https://edire.eu/?p=190	1
	Conference: Gender Equality Plans and universities of the future (January 2023)	1	https://edire.eu/?p=309	1
			https://shorturl.at/tPSXZ	1

Overcoming Obstacles and Seizing Opportunities in Europe's Research and Innovation Landscape (June, 2023)	1	https://shorturl.at/nwDP1	1
SSST and TPO Foundation: Activities within the UNIGEM Project (June 2022)	1	https://edire.eu/ssst-and-tpo-foundation-activities-within-the-unigem-project/	1
Fostering Equality, Diversity, and Inclusion in Academia: Lessons Learned and Good Practices (July 2023)	1	https://councilforeuropeanstudies.org/wp-content/uploads/2023/06/CES-Final-Conference-Program-2023.pdf https://edire.eu/fostering-equality-diversity-and-inclusion-in-academia-lessons-learned-and-good-practices/	1
Conference: Non-binary language (September 2023)	1	https://edire.eu/conference-non-binary-language/	1
EDI in BiH Academy of Arts and Science (January 2024)	1	https://edire.eu/edi-in-bih-academy-of-arts-and-science/	M18
International Day of Education or EDication (January 2024)	1	https://edire.eu/international-day-of-education-or-edication/ https://www.instagram.com/reel/C2iK8l3LmYF/?igsh=MXA5bWxxMXl4djlZg==	M18

https://www.instagram.com/reel/C2kQ_Fitp mo/?igsh=Znovd3E1Z3JmZml1
https://www.linkedin.com/posts/homework-hub-sarajevo_novabh-activity-7156981879181656064-F6sy?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_ios

Table 7: KPI for Group 4: Summer Sschools/trainings/seminars for capacity building in WP4

GROUP 4 (G4): Summer schools/trainings/seminars for capacity building organised in WP4, specifically intended for capacity building activities for developing scientific competences on EDI as well as transversal skills on fund-raising, project design and project management.	Name of the event	Indicator: N° of participants	Type of the event	Means of verification: Attendance proof, presented material, photos, events' reports.	Year/Month
Target Values: at least 2 summer schools organised, Target Values: at least 4 virtual trainings; at least 2	Introduction to HorizonEurope Programme (Sara Clavero) (September 2023)	54	training	Link 1	1
	Fundraising and Research Funding (Cinzia Leone) (September 2023)	19	training	Link 2	1
	EU projects and GEPs (Rita Bencivenga) (September 2023)	12	training	Link 3	1
	Project Management and Financial Issues (Cinzia Leone) (September 2023)	19	training	Link 4	1

	Gender Equality Resources in Academia and Research (Lucía Gloria Vázquez Rodríguez) (September 2023)	15	training	Link 5	1
	A Road to PhD Supervision, Networking, And Autonomous Work (Clara Sanchez) (September 2023)	25	training	Link 6	1
	Fulbright Foreign Student Program Training (Jose Pena Inclan) (October 2023)	21	training	Link 7	1
	Integrating gender+ intersectional approaches in the project design process (Sara Clavero) (October 2023)	17	training	Link 8	1
	Social media for success in research (Rita Bencivenga) (November 2023)	6	training	Link 9	1
	Grant Writing (Cinzia Leone) (November 2023)	11	training	Link 10	1
	ORPA training Sessions (March, April, September 2023)	5	training	LINK 11	1
	Consultative meeting: Universities and Research centres (March 2023)	15	training	Link 12	1
	Virtual Mobility Training – day I (December 2024) <i>See Annex 4</i>	25	training	Link 13	M16
	Virtual Mobility Training – day II (December 2024) <i>See Annex 4</i>	25	training	LINK 14	M16
	EDIRE PROJECT COORDINATOR AT The University of Reims Champagne-Ardenne, France (January 2024)	10	mobility/training	Link 15	M17

		"How to Select a Journal to Publish Your Research" (Aisling Coyne & Roisin Guilfoyl) (February 2024)	46	training	Link 16 Link 17	M18
Liaison activities (M6-M36)	<i>Table 8: Liaison activities</i>					
	<p>The consortium will liaise with international, EU, national, international projects on the same, or similar, issues, thus exchanging good practices and ideas, contributing to mainstreaming and then constantly updating the developed results. Particular attention will be devoted to initiatives funded in the WB, also out of the present call</p>		Project call	Indicator: N° of EU funded project addressed	Means of verification: Contents of dissemination and communication packages (D6.3 and D6.4)	Year
Target Values: at least 3 projects during the project	Embedding RRI in Western Balkan Countries: Enhancement of Self-Sustaining R&I Ecosystems	Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101006279	1	Link 1 Link 2 Link 3 Link 4	1	

		Budget-It	European Union's Horizon 2023 research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 1010904391	1	Link 5	1
		Iceland: Fostering Equality, Diversity, and Inclusion in Academia: Lessons Learned and Good Practices	Gender-Ex Project, MILIEU Project, ULYSSEUS and XFORMAL Projects	4	Link 6	1

Communication

The additional communication tools that EDIRE have been utilized:

Type	Details									
Social media (M1-M36)	<p>EDIRE social media platforms were established and used as the main communication channel for project activities to be disseminated and communicated. Social media that had been established in first month were: Facebook, Instagram, LinkedIn, Twitter and YouTube. Based on analytics, EDIRE put the focus on LinkedIn platform rather the Twitter, because the audience reach has been rapidly growing.</p> <p style="text-align: center;"><i>Table 9: KPI Social media</i></p> <table border="1" style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <tr> <td style="width: 40%; background-color: #fff9c4;"> <p>EDIRE Social Media Strategy will communicate information on ongoing activities, publications etc., to stakeholders and the public mainly through Twitter, Facebook, YouTube (other media will be considered in time, if necessary). EDIRE will use established social media accounts of EDIRE's partners to interact with target audiences and the public in all consortium countries. Established Facebook accounts will be helpful to interact with existing networks. Specific project hashtags will be selected and used for quantitative assessment. A Blog will be established, and posts will be disseminated also through social media channels</p> </td> <td style="width: 15%; background-color: #a0522d; color: white; text-align: center;">Social media</td> <td style="width: 20%; background-color: #a0522d; color: white; text-align: center;">Indicator: N° of Likes and Shares, Tweets and Retweets with certain selected hashtags</td> <td style="width: 20%; background-color: #a0522d; color: white; text-align: center;">Means of verification: reports from such networks to be kept alive via regular posting and monitoring; blog statistics</td> <td style="width: 5%; background-color: #6699cc; color: white; text-align: center;">YEAR</td> </tr> </table>					<p>EDIRE Social Media Strategy will communicate information on ongoing activities, publications etc., to stakeholders and the public mainly through Twitter, Facebook, YouTube (other media will be considered in time, if necessary). EDIRE will use established social media accounts of EDIRE's partners to interact with target audiences and the public in all consortium countries. Established Facebook accounts will be helpful to interact with existing networks. Specific project hashtags will be selected and used for quantitative assessment. A Blog will be established, and posts will be disseminated also through social media channels</p>	Social media	Indicator: N° of Likes and Shares, Tweets and Retweets with certain selected hashtags	Means of verification: reports from such networks to be kept alive via regular posting and monitoring; blog statistics	YEAR
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<p>Target Values: at least 10% increase per year after Y1 (starting from a baseline on 500 contacts per partner) as for the No of followers; at least 5 publications on the web blog (videos, photos, articles) by M36</p>		Likes	Shares/VIEWS/Impressions	Followers		Y1
	Facebook	410	25	135	LINK FB	
	Instagram	703	14	146	LINK IG	
	LinkedIn	148	20941 (imp)	199	LINK LNKD	
	Twitter		12	23	LINK X	
	Youtube	3	128	4	@edireedire	
		BLOG	Indicator: N° of publications on the web blog		Means of verification: reports from such networks to be kept alive via regular posting and monitoring; blog statistics	
		From Dublin to Sarajevo, (March 2023)	1		Blog 1	
		The Computer Science students- International Women's Day, (March 2023)	1		Blog 2	
	Complutense University team visits Sarajevo School of Science and Technology for academic exchange, (July 2023)	1		Blog 3		

	Virtual Mobility Training as seen by the SSST Academic Staff (December, 2023)	1	Blog 4	Y2
	The EDIRE team aims to have more female Nobel laureates in the coming years (December, 2023)	1	Blog 5	

Press releases and media relations (M1-M36)	EDIRE team has been using every opportunity to attend the conferences and spread the objectives of the project.				
	<i>Table 10: KPI of Press Release and Media</i>				
	Project results and relevant moments will also be communicated and disseminated through media (general press, magazines for audiences interested in EDI initiatives - women, LGBTQ+, people with disabilities- radio, television) via press releases and press briefings. Maximum geographical coverage beyond the countries represented in the consortium will be assured with a special focus on BA and other widening countries characterised by similar situations. Presentations of project results will also be issued, whenever possible, to radio and television. Besides, EDIRE will also use the freely accessible EC tools (e.g. CORDIS Wire, CORDIS News, Horizon Magazine, research*eu, "Futuris" and "Innovation" Magazines on Euronews, Athena Web) to ensure successful project communication	Press releases and media relations (M1-M36)	Indicator: N° of quotes on newspapers, television, websites; Radio and TV contributions	Means of verification: Proof of publications or videos	Year
	Target Values: At least 15 articles in either newspaper/magazines/radio by the end of the project, Target Values: at least 2 reports per year on radio/TV programmes by M36	Announcement that SSST will be coordinating the Horizon Europe project that is starting in September	portal (Klix.ba)	LINK 1	1
		Information about the project start and announcement of the Kick of Meeting	portal (Klix.ba)	LINK 2	1
Announcement of an Interview on research and science and promotion of EDIRE project by Jamsinka Hasić Telalović		Portal (N1Info)	LINK 3	1	
		TV (N1Info)	LINK 4	1	
	Portal (N1Info)	LINK 5	1		

	General information on EDIRE	website	LINK 6	1
	The conference on gender "R-Evolutions". Presentation of paper "Transforming Academia through Equality, Diversity, and Inclusion: The experience of Bosnia Herzegovina with the EDiRe project"	TV (TGR)	LINK 7	1
		website	LINK 8	1
	Interview on research and science and promotion of EDIRE project by Jamsinka Hasić Telalović	TV (BHRT)	LINK 9	1
	Interview on International Women's Day	Radio (RadioM)	LINK 10	1
			LINK 11	
	ChooseSTEMFuture RCC Campaign	website	LINK 12	1
	International Day of Education or EDication (January 2024)	TV (NOVABH; TVSA; FTV)	LINK 13	M17
			LINK 14	
			LINK 15	
			LINK 16	

Participation in Open-Science events (M6-M36)	<p>Open Science Events:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ 16 days of activism: 3 weeks of program, lectures, and workshops where EDIRE was presented. The participants had the opportunity to listen about equality, diversity, and inclusion connected to the prevention of sexual harassment and gender-based discrimination at the universities (November 2022) (https://edire.eu/16-days-of-activism-against-gender-based-violence-campaign-at-ssst/)▪ 14 Days of Bhaaas (The University of Tuzla): Know-how session and panel discussion: Overcoming Obstacles and Seizing Opportunities in Europe's Research and Innovation Landscape. The project coordinator, Jasminka Hasić Telalović, presented EDIRE by explaining the importance of Horizon programs for projects (June 2023) (https://edire.eu/navigating-the-horizon-overcoming-obstacles-and-seizing-opportunities-in-europes-research-and-innovation-landscape/)
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Table 14: Short-term Mobilities

Measurement	Receiving/Hosting Country	Institution	Name and surname of the researcher/staff	Virtual/ In Presence	Duration	Short description of the program
Short term 20/year mobilities Mid-term 25/year	Italy	University of Genoa	Amina Katica	In person	4 days	Genoa University has substantial experience with research processes and project activities that can greatly enhance SSST's work and help the EIDRE project to be organized and implemented more efficiently. Collaborating with colleagues is the best way to improve the quality of work. This meeting brought together the Office for Research and Project Administration from SSST and the Research and Grants Office at UniGe.

Table 13: Peer Reviewed Publications

Measurement	Title of publication	Authors	Link	Date	Institution
Short term 5 international publications arisen from EDIRE Mid-term 10 international publications arisen from EDIRE	Gender mainstreaming policies in Italian	G. Arena, A. C. Taramasso (UNIGE)	to be published	2024	IPPA Conference Paper
	Transforming academia through equality, diversity, and inclusion: the experience of Bosnia and Herzegovina with the EDIRE project	R. Bencivenga, C. Leone, C. M. Reale, J. Hasic Telalovic (UNIGE; SSST)	to be published	2024	in A. Tuselli, C. M.
	Autism Spectrum Disorder in Children from Bosnia and Herzegovina	Dž. Bašić, J. Hasić Telalović, L. Pašić (SSST)	to be published	2024	Microbime and Machine Learning, Volume II

Table 15: Staff-Exchange

Measurement	Receiving/Hosting Country	Institution	Name and surname of the researcher/staff	Duration	Short description of the program	Date
Short term 5/year Mid-terim 6/year	Italy	University of Genoa	Jasmina Bajramović	4 days	This meeting brought together the Office for Research and Project Administration from SSST and the Research and Grants Office at UniGe. The SSST team, Jasmina Bajramović-Malić met with their colleagues from Genoa University, who gave them an overview of the office operation. It has been agreed to cooperate on all aspects of the EIDRE project and potential future projects in a mutually beneficial way.	January 2023
	Italy	University of Genoa	Jasminka Hasić Telalović	4 days	Jasminka Hasić Telalović had a meeting with members of the Department of Informatics, Bioengineering, Robotics, and Systems Engineering. Meeting people who work in applied computer science and engineering and visiting laboratories related to robotics and automation was an honor. Also, we had the opportunity to hear more about the activities of UniGe in the biomedical domain. We had great discussions regarding the several possibilities to cooperate: Erasmus agreements/exchanges, joint/double degrees, and Ph.D. in robotics.	January 2023
	France	University of Reims Champagne-Ardenne	Jasminka Hasić Telalović	3 days	Throughout the visit, the EDIRE partners focused on discussions related to Work Package 4 (WP4), which involves Staff Exchanges, and explored possibilities for new project proposals. The visit aimed at strengthening ties and fostering collaboration between the partnering institutions, with the expectation of fruitful outcomes in the near future.	January 2024

Table 16: Project Proposals Submitted

Measurement	Name of the Project Proposal	Institution - coordinator	Institution-partners	Short description of the proposal	Budget	Funded by	Other sources
Short term 5 proposals submitted least Mid-term 12 new project proposals	Youth EU: Guidance to emancipation and autonomy of youth at risk of social exclusion in dialogue with third countries	Universidad Nacional De Educacion a Distancia	SSST University and Unidersidad Compultense de Madrid	HORIZON-MSCA-2022-SE-01	1,656.000	EU	https://www.dropbox.com/scl/fo/rex0udrrrjgbagqnxg8q/h?rlkey=z1x8er1wd6x2lv9xslpfelaaj&dl=0
	Gender roles in extremist movements		SSST University and TU Dublin	HORIZON-CL2-2024-DEMOCRACY-01-05	3,000,000	EU	

Table 17: Joint Initiative EDIRE

Measurement	Contact person/Institution/Company	Name of the Initiative	Short description	Date
Short term 1/year Mid-term 1/year	BHAAS	Overcoming Obstacles and Seizing Opportunities in Europe's Research and Innovation Landscape	Joint conference and panel discussions, attended by representatives of Ministri of Civil Affairs, University of Tuzla, canton level representatives-more opportunities for project fundings and international call applications	June, 2023
	Kick off	EDIRE PUBLIC EVENT	With two panel sessions and an engaging discussion between academics and government representatives, the SSST team led by the project coordinator, Assoc. Prof. Dr Jasminka Hasić Telalović is kickstarting the activities on the EDIRE (Equality Diversity and Inclusion for Research Enhancement in Bosnia and Herzegovina) project within the Horizon Europe scheme, funded by the European Union. (BiH panelists – Prof. Dr Aleksandra Nikolić, the Minister of Science, Higher Education and Youth of Sarajevo Canton; Prof. Dr. Jasmina Husanović from the University of Tuzla; academician Prof. Dr Mirsada Hukić from the Academy of Sciences and Art of Bosnia-Herzegovina)	sSep.22

Table 18: Training Courses

Measurement	Title of the Course	Course Trainer	Trainer Institution	Description of the training	Participants	Course Link
Short term 6 training courses on project design and management (In streaming) Mid-term 6 additional training courses (in streaming)	Introduction to HorizonEurope Programme	Sara Clavero	TUD	first steps when planning to participate in Horizon Europe projects. Discover how to identify the perfect call for your area of expertise and learn how to take action towards a successful application process.	54	https://www.dropbox.com/scl/fo/jcrtxl9dh8uz7l9ovhlge/h?rlkey=z3jkvxhmsf5uuxh49cgom6jff&dl=0
	Fundraising and Research Funding	Cinzia Leone	UNIGE	This course will present and discuss guidelines for applying for research grants and fundraising for research topics, with a particular focus on the European Framework Programme Horizon Europe. Participants are encouraged to actively engage in concrete exercises: part of the class is dedicated to participatory activities.	12	https://www.dropbox.com/scl/fo/xsp11eim1fqnk1gimiipm/h?rlkey=mkvgkx76wv8pafvs0h69tr65w&dl=0
	EU project and GEPs	Rita Bencivenga	UNIGE	In this engaging workshop, we'll be discussing the state of the art of Gender Equality Plans (GEPs) in Europe. Gain insights into their effective use and understand what is required for EU funding applications. Learn how to connect partners' GEPs to project activities, creating a reciprocal nurturing program to enhance GEPs and maximize project outcomes and outputs. Broaden your knowledge and strengthen your strategies for fostering gender+ equality within EU projects.	12	https://www.dropbox.com/scl/fo/b0vxj fog0arzwhz54wt7v/h?rlkey=o1xhcdkv5sfy0ruakd3qg8p3r&dl=0
	Project management and financial issues	Cinzia Leone	UNIGE	During the online training, we will dive into the challenges in project management and financial matters, exploring common obstacles and providing effective solutions. The training will be hosted by esteemed experts from the University of Genoa.	19	https://www.dropbox.com/scl/fo/nvcwiijg6p4j23n5njaqv/h?rlkey=8wkq9d1v8fcb79vurhl0xfayc&dl=0
	Integrating gender+ intersectional approaches in the project design process	Sara Clavero	TUD	This 3-hour training session aimed at providing support on the integration of gender+ intersectional approaches in their projects. This session is targeted at senior researchers and potential project Principal Investigators who are planning to develop a project proposal or to apply for research funding, or who are already in the process of developing a project proposal.	17	https://www.dropbox.com/scl/fo/mhs1rvy5omc8zvfxdsmm6/h?rlkey=zomy9whjc2mbui41xgz8vm2nb&dl=0
	Grant Writing	Cinzia Leone	UNIGE	The seminar will offer important insights and tips for grant writing: success stories and features which will help you draft a grant proposal.	11	https://www.dropbox.com/scl/fo/s7ph8hkiq6g6boj4vk48/h?rlkey=h1dh0og1st2ozm3du3o52chq2&dl=0
	Identifying partnership opportunities for European projects	Liisa Irene Hänninen, Cristina Perez, Patricia Nunez	UCM	ORPA TRAININGS SESSIONS	4	https://www.dropbox.com/scl/fo/qv4xjr0xcz7aevhly78f5/h?rlkey=g8ynlwmfftclwj9u4srihy97n&dl=0

4 Exploitation and sustainability of results

The task aims at maximizing results' exploitation by taking all emerging opportunities to mainstream the results achieved and ensure their transferability and sustainability. Partners defined individual plans for results' exploitation by M3, when the first version of the dissemination, communication and exploitation and sustainability plan was delivered (D6.1). The exploitation plan will be revised and updated during the project and submitted in its final version in M36 (D6.5). The final version will pay particular attention to ensure the sustainability of the main EDIRE twinning mechanisms, identifying adequate mechanisms to:

- 1) formalise the staff exchange mechanism with formal international cooperation agreements;
- 2) set-up joint doctorates on EDIRE themes;
- 3) maintain operational the summer school and the training activities developed by the project for the benefit of other BA institutions. All partners will embed lessons learnt in EDIRE in their institutional activities.

Concerning the IPR, EDIRE will develop all the results and the inherent publications following the open access policy, with due confidentiality obligations regarding the personal data. All EDIRE publications, data elaborations and results will be available for all, open and public. All project results arising from the project and likely to be exploited have been protected according to the CA to be signed by all partners. The document addresses different issues like confidentiality, access, and ownership of key knowledge and IPR management, whose general approaches are described in Sect. 2.2.3.

EDIRE is the first Horizon Europe coordinated by an institution in Bosnia and Herzegovina and an opportunity to strengthen the country's participation in this programme. As a result of planned EDIRE activities, SSST has been developing research collaboration with at least 10 other research performing institutions in Bosnia and Herzegovina. The knowledge and experience transferred from EDIRE's EU partners have been shared in this network and have been used to foster creation of new projects that strengthen the (EDI) research capabilities and outcomes in the country. In addition, the links established through liaising with other European projects will further enlarge SSST's (as well as Bosnia and Herzegovina's) network.

The activities will thus include:

- future collaborations and other activities – project, seminars, conferences;
- meetings of doctoral programmes and engagement of doctoral students;

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- the newly established scientific communication unit has been developed the skills to talk to media.

UCM has several owned media channels for the project exploitation which include a radio station, a newspaper, faculty website news, social media (twitter, LinkedIn, Facebook) which will be used for sharing results among the academic community of the University. External means include a special office for academic exploitation run by experts that have been released a large national news release about the project results. Also, institutional websites among the academic community, such as the ITC (Institute for the Technology of Knowledge) will distribute EDIRE results. Also, project results will be made available through conferences at ITC and other scientific meetings at the University.

Furthermore, project main topics, key milestones and results have been shared with academic and scientific community at UCM with interdisciplinary research groups, the School of Doctoral and Postgraduate Programmes, as well as with the Unit of Scientific Communication. The Summer School hosted by UCM in M21 will be open to postgraduate students at UCM to foster international research and networking opportunities.

All project partners will be invited to contribute to the monthly blog published by RINCE to communicate results to the Irish HE community and beyond. Similarly, the more scientific results of the EDIRE project will be presented at the RINCE seminar series, running monthly. An exchange programme between SSST and TU Dublin R&I offices will be set up as a mutual learning and knowledge exchange mechanism, with the goal of integrating EDIRE's results in the research policy of both institutions.

The project scope, main milestones and results have been shared by UniGe with the academic, student and civil communities in different ways. They will be presented along with the UniGe Equal Opportunities Committee activities and in gender-research-specific seminars and workshops periodically held to incentive studies and sensibility on this topic. In addition, a cycle of recordings in English is planned for UniGe Radio. This web radio can be reached via the internet from all over the planet and will be used to share worldwide the project results and podcasts. In this cycle of recording, the project will be presented along with its main results and milestones. The recordings, although coordinated by the EDIRE UniGe team, will be operated by students, both in the role of 'apprentice journalists' and interviewees, for a better understanding of students' perceptions of the topics raised by the project. URCA has a very active communication service that provides several communication solutions: Newsletter, Press Relations, Organization of institutional events, Website, and Several social media (Twitter, Facebook, LinkedIn...). The URCA team interacts with this service for sharing results among the academic community of the URCA, other French universities and other strategic actors. The research groups of the URCA group members will use the websites of their departments and research groups to distribute EDIRE results. Some results of the EDIRE project will be submitted to national and international ITC conferences at ITC and journal. The URCA group will also contact the different departments and master's to share the main topics and results of EDIRE.

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4.1 Overall Outline

An outline of the EDIRE dissemination, communication, and exploitation strategy for the three years of the project is described here:

Table 11: Two-year plan

Period	Stage	Goal	Activities
Update 1 M1 Sept. 2022 – M18 Feb. 2024	Execution of dissemination and communication, Exploitation strategy planning	Originate project identity and presence. Dissemination of knowledge and finding.	Logo and visual identity; identification of stakeholders and communication tools; design of promotional material, branding, and stationary; Dissemination and communication plan through M18 of the project.
			Social media and website content planning; establishing social media; attending first meetings, workshops, and conferences with a view to networking; EDIRE website launch, advertise website; publishing of three Project Newsletters on EDIRE website; dissemination, communication, and exploitation plan through M36.
			Mid-term dissemination event (M18)- Spain; promotion of the first summer school; focused presentations at targeted conferences; the beginning of scientific dissemination, and communication on selected public media channels.
			Revision of the Dissemination, communication, and exploitation plan.
Update 2 M19 March 2023 – M36 Aug. 2025	The exploitation of results	Dissemination of knowledge and findings, Invitation to act.	Publishing of the additional three Project Newsletters on the EDIRE website.
			Heavily promote EDIRE final dissemination event (M35), Second summer school, and Mediterranean forum; Engage people to participate in the final event of EDIRE; make plans for the website publishing after the realization of the project.
			Exploitation and sustainability plan - final version.

5 Summary outline

Activity	To be completed by M36
Project visual identity	Continually use designs for all communication, dissemination, and exploitation activities.
Website	All sections regularly filled with the relevant data and indicated measures achieved.
Publications, including scientific articles will be published in international peer-reviewed indexed journals, respecting the Open Access policy	The publication plan executed.
Newsletter	M24, M30, M36
Project meetings	M21: Madrid M30: Online (Reims to organize open event) M35: Sarajevo
Dissemination event	M35: Final dissemination event
Events external to the consortium activities	Plan through M35
<i>Summer-schools/trainings</i>	Trainings completed according to the plan.
<i>Social media</i>	Meeting the planned success indicators.
<i>Press release</i>	Meeting the planned success indicators.
<i>Open science events</i>	Meeting the planned success indicators.

Annexes

Annex 1

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INTEGRATING EDI PRINCIPLES AND PRACTICES IN HIGHER EDUCATION AND BEYOND: INTERNATIONAL AND MULTI-SECTORAL PERSPECTIVES

Speakers

- Catherine Bolger (GBV, TUDublin)
- Philip Owende (Race Equity, TUDublin)
- Bob O'Mhurcu (Gender Identity and Gender Expression, TUDublin)
- Yvonne Galligan (Athena Swan, TUDublin)
- Catherine Deegan (UDL, TuDublin)
- Beatrice Avolio (Pontifical Catholic University of Peru)
- Jasminka Hasić Telalović (Sarajevo School of Science and Technology)
- Denis Doolan (AIB - TBC)

October 17th
Time: 9.30am-1pm (Irish Standard Time)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe program for widening participation and spreading excellence under Grant Agreement number 101060145

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Funded by the European Union **EDiRE**

INTEGRATING EDI PRINCIPLES AND PRACTICES IN HIGHER EDUCATION AND BEYOND: INTERNATIONAL AND MULTI-SECTORAL PERSPECTIVES

Open Session
October 17th 2023
9.30am-1pm (Irish Standard Time)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe program for widening participation and spreading excellence under Grant Agreement number 101060145

AGENDA

EDIRE Open Session

Integrating EDI principles and practices in Higher Education and beyond: International and multi-sectoral perspectives

Date: 17 October 2023

Time: 9.30am-1pm (Irish Summer Time)

Venue: St Laurence's Church, TU Dublin, Grangegorman

Description: As part of the EDIRE project (Equality Diversity and Inclusion for Research Enhancement in Bosnia Herzegovina), funded by Horizon Europe, TU Dublin will host an Open Session with the aim to promote the exchange and dissemination of EDI good practice in Higher Education Institutions and beyond. How can we navigate and benefit from increasingly intersectional perspectives on EDI? How can we collaborate with partners from across Europe to enhance EDI experiences and expertise? What can we learn from EDI thinking and practice in sectors other than Higher Education? The event will present experiences in Ireland (both in Higher Education and the private sector), Bosnia & Herzegovina, Italy and Sweden to discuss achievements, barriers, future challenges and how to overcome them.

Programme:

- 9.30- 9.40 Welcome and introduction – Sara Clavero, TU Dublin
- 9.40- 11.00 EDI initiatives at TU Dublin (moderated by Sara Clavero, TU Dublin)
Catherine Bolger (**GBV**); Philip Owende (**Race Equity**), Bob O'Mhurcu (**Gender Identity and Gender Expression**); Catherine Deegan (**UDL**)
- 11.00 - 11.20 Coffee break
- 11.20- 12.00 'European Perspectives on EDI in HE: Reflections and Lessons from Bosnia and Herzegovina and Italy'
Jasminka Hasic, Sarajevo School of Science and Technology, and Angela Celeste Taramasso, University of Genoa (moderated by Caitriona Delaney, TU Dublin)
- 12.00- 12.30 'Embedding EDI principles in the Irish NGO sector' – Jeanne McDonagh Open Doors Initiative
- 12.30- 12.55 Q&A (moderated by Caitriona Delaney, TU Dublin)
- 12.55-13.00 Wrap-up and conclusions – Sara Clavero, TU Dublin
- 13.00- 14.00 Lunch

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Annex 2

II Project Meeting and Panel discussion: Research, University, Gender and EDI policies

Funded by the European Union

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Sarajevo School of Science and Technology | DUBLIN | Università di Genova | UNIVERSITÉ DE REIMS CHAMPAGNE-ARDENNE | UNIVERSIDAD COMPLUTENSE MADRID

RESEARCH, UNIVERSITY, GENDER AND EDI POLICIES

Speakers

Prof. dr. Lyuba Spasova, Institute of Philosophy and Sociology at the Bulgarian Academy of Science, Bulgaria

Prof. dr. Sarina Bakić, Department of Sociology, Faculty of the Political Science, University of Sarajevo, B&H

Prof. dr. Davide Peddis, Department of Chemistry and Industrial Chemistry, University of Genova, Italy

Prof. dr. Paolo Piccardo, Department of Chemistry and Industrial Chemistry, University of Genova, Italy

Moderator

Prof. dr. Jasminka Hasić Telalović, SSST

16 02 Zoom 12:30 - 13:30

Time: 12:30-13:30 CET Zoom (<https://ssst.zoom.us/j/7899490449>)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe program for widening participation and spreading excellence under Grant Agreement number 101060145

Annex 3

Steering Committee Meeting – agenda example

AGENDA

Equality Diversity and Inclusion for Research Enhancement in Bosnia Herzegovina

Meeting: Steering Committee EDIRE

Time and Date: November 29, 2023, 09.30 AM (CET)

Venue: Online ZOOM:

<https://ssst.zoom.us/j/7899490449>

Meeting ID: 789 949 0449

1. Updates from WP leaders
 - a. **WP2** Strategic Research Component on EDI (TU Dublin)
 - b. **WP4** Boosting Scientific Excellence at SSST (URCA)
 - i. Virtual Mobility Training SSST (for academic staff and EDIRE partners presentations)
 - ii. Other trainings
 - c. **WP5** Expertise development in research management and fundraising (UNIGE)
2. Ongoing deliverables
 - a. **D 7.3** (deadline November 30)
3. Upcoming deliverables (M18 – February 2024)
 - a. **D 4.2** Mid-term progress report and evaluation of the twinning mechanisms (M18, URCA)
 - b. **D 5.2** Interim report and evaluation on the expertise development activities (M18, UNIGE)
 - c. **D 6.2** Dissemination, communication and exploitation package - RP1 (M18, SSST)
4. **WP1** Coordination, management, ethics and evaluation (SSST)
 - a. Midterm Report – preparations
 - b. Project Review (February 16, 2024, 11:00 am CET)
5. **WP6** – Outreach, exploitation and Sustainability (SSST, to discuss and review)

Annex 4

Virtual Mobility Training Event – agenda

AGENDA

Virtual Mobility Training - SSST University Academic Staff

Monti, Igman
1.12.2023
2.12.2023

Zoom link:
<https://ssst.zoom.us/j/7899490449>

Meeting ID: 789 949 0449

1 day

12:30 Welcoming

13:30 EDIRE HorizonEurope Project Introduction - Prof. Jasminka Hasić Telalović, Project Coordinator

13:45 Coffee and snacks

14:00 EDIRE Consortium Partners (Zoom link)

14:00 The University of Reims Champagne-Ardenne, France

- Introduction of URCA and a few labs by Juliet Chebet Moso, juliet-chebet.moso@univ-reims.fr
- Biomaterials and inflammation in bone sites (BIOS) by Sophie Gangloff, sophie.gangloff@univ-reims.fr, or Juliet Chebet Moso
- HPC and Computer Graphics by Luiz Angelo Steffanel, luiz-angelo.steffanel@univ-reims.fr
- IOT, AI and Applications by Zahia Guessoum, Zahia.Guessoum@univ-reims.fr

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